

Environmental Tipping Points: Human Impact, Ecological Disruption, and Sustainability Challenges

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Abstract- Environmental tipping points represent critical thresholds within ecological and climate systems, beyond which significant and often irreversible changes occur. Driven largely by human activities such as deforestation, fossil fuel combustion, pollution, and overexploitation of natural resources, these tipping points threaten the stability of the Earth's life-support systems. Key examples include the collapse of coral reef ecosystems, the thawing of permafrost, and disruptions to major oceanic and atmospheric circulation patterns. These shifts are often accelerated by positive feedback loops, making them difficult to reverse once triggered. This paper explores the mechanisms behind environmental tipping points, identifies major systems at risk, and examines the profound ecological, social, and economic consequences of crossing these thresholds. It also highlights the urgent need for integrated, science-based sustainability strategies aimed at mitigating human impacts and building resilience within natural systems. Preventing the crossing of critical tipping points is not only an ecological imperative but also a central challenge for the future of humanity.

Index Terms- Environmental tipping points, Ecological thresholds, Climate change, Biodiversity loss, Ecosystem collapse, Human impact, Sustainability

I. INTRODUCTION

Earth used to break and remake itself from eternity. And to date, it's carrying on this process. But the one thing is now technologies are also causing a change in the environment, however, this shouldn't happen. Humans are the best creation of nature but the creation of humans causes damage to our mother nature. This 21st century is very much beneficial for humans and its creation but somehow this tech century damaging all the natural resources. Overuse of anything even in past has not proven beneficial for mankind. Day by day situations is getting out of human control. With the help of science and technology, we can survive but this is also should be taken into consideration that all the free resources that we are getting from the earth and use cannot be replenishable. That day isn't too far where we can't even able to take a breath freely. Even the situation of covid directly points out how much helpless would be a human being if nature comes to protest against the revolution. And in near future, we are also going to suffer from the Unplanned and limitless use of natural resources like fossil fuels, natural gases, and many more. For the seek of urbanization mile after miles of forests were destroyed and the results are not too good.

II. MAJOR ENVIRONMENTAL PROBLEMS OF 2025

Deforestation

We can define deforestation as the large-scale removal of trees from forests for urbanization. It is a serious environmental concern since it can result in the loss of biodiversity, damage to natural habitats, disturbances in the water cycle, and soil erosion. Deforestation is also has a contribution to climate change and global warming.

Causes of Deforestation

Trees are an essential part of the whole environment system they use to produce oxygen which is a necessary element for the whole of humankind. We also get lots of resources from the trees along with food and wood. But whenever there arise shortages of land in the world miles after miles of forests are burnt. This not only causes damage to the forest but also to the species in it. If we take an example of the biggest industry in India it is usually established after deforestation. It is also witnessed by history. For example, when railways in India were established, it causes deforestation too. Because of this deforestation, India got it's the biggest transport system in the whole world. Railways account for barely 1.2 per cent of global carbon dioxide emissions from transport, which itself

accounted for 24 per cent of all emissions globally(1). After Railways within ten years, this tree become endangered species in India. However, India claims to be the biggest production house of “Mehogoni” as well as other specific woods like “Chandan”, and” Seguin” which are rare in the world but common in India. Thus, deforestation takes away this pride. Not only that many rarest species of animals, birds and mammals’ habitats become endangered in nature.

Another rare species of tree in India is the “Mangrove” it is founded in east coastal areas where soils are soft and contain salt. These trees protect these soils from erosion as well as protect the bank of the river. Somehow deforestation also paws into the land of “Mangrove”. Now the banks are left unprotected and many islands in east coastal are drawn into the sea and many are on the way to drowning in near future.

This is not about only India in the whole world the scenarios are the same. The submerged Island where part of the Solomon Island will be drawn in near future and many more such examples are there. Once in a research article, it is said: “confirms the numerous anecdotal accounts from Pacific of the dramatic impacts of climate change in coastlines and people. The missing island ranging in size from 1 to 5 hectares in near future” (2). And it is also found that the highest deforestation rate is in Brazil, where every three minutes a forest is uprooted. Indonesia is in the second position and in third comes Mexico City.

Mining and urban expansion are other reasons for deforestation. The environmental impact of mining includes soil erosion, formation of sinkholes, biodiversity degradation and impurity of groundwater. Mining occurs to extract precious metals such as Manganese, tantalum and many more. But at the same time mining is a destructive activity that damages the rainforest ecosystem and causes problems for local peoples.

Fig 1: Scenarios of the world’s population

Civil Wars

Wars are an inevitable part of human traits. From the very beginning of this journey, they start fighting for the power of

the crown. This “Game of Thrown” may decide the powerful person or country but it is evident that human is still very much far from civilization. Weapons they have used in earlier days were made up of stone and wood and later metals. But the world walked some extra miles and now they use atoms bombs and bioweapons. Which can able to destroy a country at a time and also uprooted its infrastructure. The atomic bombings of Hiroshima and Nagasaki have already proven the. To date, even a child was born with some extraordinary difficulties due to the atomic effect of bombarding in world wars. Nowadays many powerful countries use atomic bombs to dominate other countries it’s not only destroying the country but its biodiversity of it at the same time. It was reported that 15% of the world’s biodiversity permanently disappear from the earth due to the usage of atomic bombs. (3)

Now, another most powerful weapons of the youth of technology are Bioweapons. It is a hundred times more effective than atoms bombs. Already many countries start using this weapon on other countries. A bioweapon is a micro-organism such as a virus, protozoan, bacterium, or fungus that can purposefully be turned into a weapon and applied against humans during wars. Self-replicating toxins and pathogens can also be turned into bioweapons with devastating effects. There exist an estimated 1,200 different kinds of bioagents that have already been weaponized or have the potential to be got turned into a bioweapon. More than 500 million people have died of infectious diseases in the past century, and most have been due to this to bioweapons. The first pathogens and toxins were applied in the war were 1763 when the British soldiers used smallpox against the Native American Indians at the time of the French and Indian war. This whole system of using bioweapons is known as biological warfare. And the future is not too far when we have to pay for our living.

Air Pollution

The effects of air pollution in India are only getting worse as by time passes. The worsening effects can only be the result of the increasing amount of air pollution in India as well as other countries. Air pollution is the 5th biggest cause of death in India. In 2010, air pollution killed 1.5 million people in India, which is six times greater than the number of deaths from air pollution in 2000. About 1/6 of 3.2 million deaths due to outdoor air pollution came from India(4). Therefore, not only can the air in India take lives, but it can also lead to other life-threatening diseases. The air in India can cause many diseases to anyone. Several terrifying diseases are directly connected with air pollution, such as cardiovascular diseases, respiratory infections and cancer. Pollutant particles are the main reason for heart and lung diseases in India. In India, twenty per cent of lung cancer is caused by air pollution and thirteen per cent of hospitalized children die from acute respiratory infections. Also, high vehicular pollution is the cause of the increase of children with attention-deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD).

The World Health Organization has declared that there is a direct connection between diesel evaporation and cancer.

The ill-effects of air pollutant emissions could impact biological diversity. Though it is this is not so evident but many researchers found that impurities in the air cause damage to biodiversity. Acid rain, which is a result of air pollution, is caused by the oxidation and evaporation of SO₂ and NO_x emissions in the atmosphere. Therefore, acid rain can have harmful effects on our biodiversity. Nitrogen deposition in plants is a serious outcome of air pollution.

Ozone is another pollutant that is toxic to both plants and animals. Ozone results in reduced photosynthesis and slower growth in plants. In animals and humans, ozone can affect the lung tissues causing respiratory conditions, such as asthma. Some researchers evaluated the plant India's losses in crop yield and financial problems incurred during 2014–15 due to the ozone. Poor air quality and exposure to anthropogenic pollution hurt the health of animals as well.

Moreover, the reproductive performance of animals also gets affected due to increased oxidative stress, thereby impacting the population of any species. This may not prove healthy, especially for the endangered species. Considering the rapid urbanisation, more focus should be given to this study area in the future.

Fig 2: Burning of waste materials

Overuse of Fossil Fuels

For the eternity of civilization, humankind uses fossil fuels in every single scientific application. After a certain period, there will inevitably be no fossil fuel will be left to use. And this is what is known as non-renewable energy resources. Once these resources are over it is over. Instead of this, we can use renewable energy resources like solar power but it is not worthy as fuels are.

But overuse of fossil fuels not only causes shortages of resources but played a huge role in pollution. The uncontrollable burning of fossil fuels caused air pollution.

Poisons gases like carbon dioxide, nitrogen dioxide and sulphur dioxide are produced and mixed with air. Which later causes many difficulties for humans as well as the environment. Day by day temperature of the earth is increasing causing global warming. Which later created lots of odds in the growth of whole human traits.

There have been various efforts to study the air quality in Indian cities. The potential of the atmospheric carcinogenic emissions to put human health at risk. According to this study, out of 18 megacities considered worldwide, the Indian cities, namely, Delhi, Kolkata, and Mumbai(5). It also evaluated the vehicular emissions in Kolkata between 2000 and 2010 and inferred that the older vehicles in the city contributed more to the pollution load and should be phased out. And these cause severe damage to the agricultural fields in India. Which is also a threatening sign for Indians. The government's decision to adopt compressed natural gas (CNG) as an alternative fuel to petrol and diesel, thus in Delhi this policy has already been taken into care and all the vehicles are in strict vigilance. Moreover, the increasing number of studies related to this field shows the importance of research on this subject. Several had been done on this air pollution across several cities in India. However, there is an urgent need for a comprehensive review of the existing issues in the Indian scenario. More focus is needed on studying the impacts of this pollutant on various forms, such as the ecosystem, biodiversity and human health.

A comprehensive review is done to understand the current scenario in the Indian context. The section contains a detailed review focused on air pollution studies in India, the various sources, and the effects of the pollutants on the ecosystem, biodiversity and human health. The various air quality standards followed by countries worldwide are included as well.

Transport Emissions

Transportation is the main contributor to air pollutants in almost every city, but this phenomenon is worse in urban cities. This could be due to the increased number of vehicles when compared to the existing infrastructural facilities, such as roads, fuel stations, and the number of passenger terminals provided for public transport. In India, the amount of motorised transport increased day by day. A significant share of vehicular emissions is noticed in urban cities, such as Delhi, Mumbai, Bengaluru, and Kolkata.

Carbon monoxide, Chlorofluorocarbon and nitrogen oxides are the major pollutants of vehicular emissions. In an urban environment, road traffic emissions are one of the prime reasons behind air pollution. Lots of major air pollutant also comes out from the vehicle manufacturing companies and those are more dangerous.

Industrial Processes

Over the last few years, India has witnessed large-scale industrialisation. This has degraded the air quality in most urban cities. The Central Pollution Control Board (CPCB) has categorised the polluting industries into 17 types, which fall under the small and medium scale. Out of these categories, seven have been marked as 'critical' industries including iron and steel, sugar, paper, cement, fertiliser, copper, and aluminium. The major pollutants comprise oxides of carbon, nitrogen and sulphur.

The small-scale industries, which are not regulated like the major industries, use several energy sources other than the primary source of state-provided electricity. Some of these fuels include the use of biomass, plastic, and crude oil. These energy sources are neglected in the current emission inventory studies. In India, a major fraction of the pollution load comes from the brick manufacturing industries, which are situated on the outskirts of the city. Rajkot (42%) and Pune (30%) are the two cities where industries play a prominent role in contributing to the highest amount of air pollutants(6).

Agriculture

Agricultural activities produce emissions, which have the potential to pollute the environment. Ammonia and nitrous oxide are the key pollutants released from agricultural activities. The other agricultural emissions include methane emissions from enteric fermentation processes, nitrogen excretions from animal manure, such as Methane, Nitrous oxide, and Ammonia emissions from wetlands, and nitrogen emissions from agricultural soils due to the addition of fertilisers and other residues to the soil. Agricultural processes, such as 'slash and burn' are prime reasons for photochemical smog resulting from the smoke generated during the process. Crop residue burning is another process that results in toxic pollutant emissions. This is how neighbouring cities of Delhi contribute to the agricultural pollution load. This is an example of how external sources contribute to the menace of air pollution in the city.

Power Plants

The contribution of power plants to air emissions in India is both immense and worrisome. The thermal power plants manufacture around 74% of the total power generated in India(7). According to The Energy and Resources Institute (TERI), the emissions of air pollutants are doubled. Thermal power plants are also producing some oxides which cause pollution, thereby contributing significantly to the emission inventories. Thus, there is an urgent need to adopt alternative power sources including green and renewable resources for meeting the energy requirements.

Waste Treatment and Biomass Burning

In India, about 80% of municipal solid waste (MSW) is still discarded into open dumping yards and landfills, which leads

to various poisonous gases emissions apart from that it also causes poor water quality and also caused soil pollution. The lack of proper treatment of municipalities and corporation biomass burning are the reason causing air pollution in urban cities as well as in rural areas. Methane is the major pollutant released from landfills and wastewater treatment plants. Ammonia is another by-product, which is released from the composting process. The open burning of wastes, including plastic, produces toxic and carcinogenic emissions which can cause difficulties for humans as well as animals and other living entities on this planet.

Table 1: Air quality standards of various countries worldwide (WHO 2005)

Pollutant	Time	WHO	European Union	United States	California	Japan	India	South Africa	India (I)	China (II)
Sulphur dioxide (µg/m ³)	1 year		125	75		80	75	50	1500/80	2000/100
	24h		250	150		165	145	125	3000/120	30/150/250
	1h		500	300		342				150/500/700
Nitrogen dioxide (µg/m ³)	1 year		40	40		100		34	1500/80	4000/80
	24h		80	80		118		188	3000/120	8000/120
	1h		200	200		470		374		120/120/240
PM ₁₀ (µg/m ³)	1 year		20	40		50	30	50	50/60/120	40/100/130
	24h		50*	50*		150	50	120	188	40/100/130
	1 year		10	15		12		15		50/150/230
PM _{2.5} (µg/m ³)	1 year		25	60		60		60		
	24h		50	120		120		120		
	1h		150	350		350		350		
Carbon monoxide (ppm)	1 year		35	35		11	45	30	4	10
	24h		70	70		22	90	60	8	
	1h		175	175		55	216	233		

* Not to exceed more than 3 days per year; ** Not to exceed more than 35 days per year; † Photochemical oxidants; ‡ Sensitive population; § Residential population; ¶ Industrial population; Class I tourist, historical, and conservation areas; Class II residential urban and rural areas; Class III industrial and heavy traffic areas

Fig 3: Index of various pollutants worldwide

Domestic Sector

Households are considered a major contributor to pollution in India. The emissions from fossil fuel burning, stoves affect the overall air quality. Domestic energy mostly depends on fuels, such as cooking gas, kerosene, wood, crop wastes or cow dung cakes.

Though liquefied petroleum gas (LPG) is used as an alternative source of cooking fuel in most urban cities, the major share of India's rural population continues to rely on cow dung cakes, biomass, charcoal or wood as the primary fuel for cooking and other energy purposes and demands. Which are the biggest supplier of carbon dioxide in the air.

III. PROBLEMS DUE TO ENVIRONMENTAL CONDITIONS

Problems with non-renewable Energy

As we all know the origin of non-renewable energy resources is limited and it will be an end in near future. In the laboratory, we cannot able to make fossil fuels as it is a long process and at the same time demand is too high to produce. From the period of the creation of the earth, it uses to collect all these resources and which turned into this energy resources. But the problem is even bigger than this. In every science and technology we use non-renewable energy. Though

scientists invented renewable energy resources these usually produce lesser energy than non-renewable.

Endangered Species

The term “Biodiversity” was coined by Walter Rosen in 1986(8). This means variation of the species along with the change of location as well as other entities. Moreover, many scientists agreed that variation is the thing to continue in this world. It is intraspecies as well as inter species. And where these diversities are more in number WHO recognise those places as “Hotspot”. India has mainly four hotspots East Himalayan range, North Himalayan range, Paschim Ghat range, South coastal range. Where the total number of endangered species is more than 70%. Thing is that these diversities have a direct contribution to India’s economy as well as natural stability. But due to uprising pollution, this species is in danger rather these Hotspots are in danger. Due to air pollution, lots of species of birds become extinct. Somehow this pollution affects natural selection and which affect directly in natural growth. And this directly affects the economy of the country due to less variation growth of crops would be less and this increases the price in the market. And this could be a great challenge for a country like India where 70% of its economy depends upon harvesting.

During the decade that just ended (2010-2019), the International Union for the Conservation of Nature (IUCN) declared the extinction of 160 species. (9). Some of the extinct species of plants are:

- Saint Helena Olive, this plant did not belong to the family of olives. Instead, it was a plant with pale “pink flowers” that bloomed on the small island of England(10). Their population was very few at that time also, but later it completely disappeared. And it was also the main resource of food for many bird species of those islands.
- And many more left to take the name. Not only plant species now we are going to give some examples of extinct animals in India as well as other countries
- The Indian Cheetah is also labelled as a critically endangered species in India. Currently, it survives only in the regions of Iran and some other protected areas. These Indian or Asiatic Cheetahs come from the family of the African Cheetahs, but they are a little different from them.
- DODO was a bird. Very little information is found about Dodo. The primary reason for being extinct was the abundance of food(11). However, they made them easy prey for sailors and their domestic animals. This was the reason why Dodo became extinct within a century of its discovery.

Fig 4: Extinct Dodo Bird

Climate Change

Nowadays the most unpredictable word is climate. Climate change is a major crisis now which triggers more frequent droughts. Huge flooding is also one of the consequences of climate change. As an example we can say India’s north-west coast to the south-eastern coastal region have experienced huge rainfall. Day by day dry years are expected to be drier and wet years wetter. Environmentalists claim that some parts of South Asia have become drier in the last 10 years along with the increasing number of droughts. As a result India’s crop area are getting effected.

Sea Level Rise

Mumbai, the city has the world’s largest population exposed to coastal flooding, with large parts of the city built on reclaimed land, below the high-tide mark. Rapid and unplanned urbanization further increases the risks of seawater intrusion. With India close to the equator, the sub-continent would see much higher rises in sea levels than higher latitudes. Sea-level rise and storm surges would lead to saltwater intrusion in the coastal areas, impacting agriculture, degrading groundwater quality, contaminating drinking water, and possibly causing a rise in diarrhoea cases and cholera outbreaks, as the cholera bacterium survives longer in saline water so it’s a time taking process to battle against it. Kolkata and Mumbai, both immensely populated cities, are particularly vulnerable to the impacts of sea-level rise, tropical cyclones, and flooding.

Fig 5: Various accounts of pollution

IV. AGRICULTURE AND FOOD SECURITY

Even if there is no climatic disorder price of food will also increase due to some inevitable reason. But this climatic change becomes the third person to affect the production of crops. Two major crops of India are rice and wheat let us briefly discuss the conditions.

Rice: Overall rice yields have increased but this rising temperatures with lower rainfall at the end of the growing season have caused a significant loss in India's rice production. Without climate change, this rice production may increase.

Wheat: Recent studies show that wheat is the main production of India as well as Bangladesh. Observations show that extremely high temperatures in northern India, have had a substantial negative effect on wheat production, and rising temperatures are only the cause of it. Another part is the scarcity of water and which also affects the production of wheat. Should current trends persist, substantial yield reductions in both rice and wheat can be expected in the near and medium-term.

Energy Plants Security

Impacts on water resources can undermine the two dominant forms of power generation in India - hydropower and thermal power generation, both of which depend on water supplies to function effectively. To function at full efficiency, thermal power plants need a constant supply of fresh cool water to maintain their cooling systems. The increasing problems and permanent decreases in river streams can pose a major challenge to hydropower plants and increase the risk of physical damage from landslides, floods, outbursts of glacial lakes, and other climate-related natural disaster. Decreases in the availability of fresh water and increases in temperature will pose major risk factors to thermal power generation.

Water Crisis

Many parts of India are already experiencing water stress. Even without climate change, satisfying future demand for water will be a major challenge. Urbanization, population growth, economic development, and increasing demand for water from agriculture and industry are likely to aggravate the situation further. An increase in variability of monsoon rainfall is expected to increase water shortages in some areas. Studies have found that the threat to water security is very high over central India, along with the mountain ranges of the Western Ghats, and in India's north-eastern states.

Health Issues

Climate change is expected to have major health impacts in India- increasing malnutrition and related health disorders such as child stunting - with the poor likely to be affected most severely. Malaria and other vector-borne diseases, along

with diarrheal infections which are a major cause of child mortality, are likely to spread into areas where colder temperatures had previously limited transmission. Heatwaves are likely to result in a very substantial rise in mortality and death, and injuries from extreme weather events are likely to increase. The Health system must be improved to improve.

V. CONCLUSION

Environmental conditions of the 21st century are getting worsen day by day. The world already witnessed climatic changes as well as witnessed pandemics like Covid-19. For two years they are captivated at their places and for these two years, its stepped back forty years which is not at all acceptable for human growth and future development. To live in future, we have to secure our present and as a responsible citizen our primary duty is to take care of the upcoming generation, to build a world where they could breadth easily, lead a pollution-free healthy life. But somehow the current situation of the environment opposes our duties. Today's world is not a safe place for mankind this increasing pollution may cost us our lives. Climate change, degradation of biodiversity, deforestation, shortages of non-renewable energy resources somehow point out the ending of a species. People always wanted to lead a calm and relaxed life all the scientific inventions at least pointing this fact. And this makes people lazy generation after generation. We all have to understand that where we live we also should take care of that place. Nature is our mother and without harming it we should take care of our mother nature for us only. We have to progress but without causing damage to the world and also we have to compensate for whatever we did. It is a matter of great concern that a large part of the world's most polluted cities are located in India. United Nations Secretary-General António Guterres said "Our planet is changing before our eyes — from the ocean depths to mountain tops; from melting glaciers to relentless extreme weather events," in the opening ceremony of the COP26 U.N. Climate Summit in Glasgow, Scotland (12). He also added Either we have to stop pollution or pollution will stop us. We are digging our own graves Guterres warned. Our Prime Minister Narendra Modi shared India's vision at COP-26 that India will achieve net zero carbon emissions by 2070. Developed countries are now blaming developing countries for their carbon emissions, but it should not be forgotten that developed countries have also released huge amount of carbon in the past and have strengthened their economies. Developed countries should admit the truth and try to save the environment by cooperating with all developing countries. Because its high time. To live on this planet earth we have to stop hammering its nature. The public and government also should work unitedly to fight back and make the world a better place.

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